

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Selamat**FIRST NAME:** Mohamad Faiz**PROGRAM CODE:** DSDD**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 1**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied U.K. conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: Pages (Mac) converted to Word Document

List of key concepts with page number in text:

1. The Basics of Essay Writing (EUCLID 2021, 1-4)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 5-6)
3. Personal vs Academic Style (EUCLID 2021, 12)
4. Rules of Thumb for Writing Papers (EUCLID 2021, 14)
5. Style Guide (EUCLID 2019, 25-26)
6. CMS Crib Sheet (EUCLID 2019, 44-55)

COMMON 'LANGUAGE' FOR COMMUNICATION

1) INTRODUCTION

As my native language is English and I had completed by past bachelor's and master's degrees in English. I initially found the curriculum for academic writing to be excessive and draining. I wondered how such arduous structures would contribute towards the achievement of my goal, which is to advocate and implement sustainable development practices in Southeast Asia.

However, as I delved deeper into the course materials, I started to better appreciate the value of rigour and referencing of papers to establish certain points or positions. As a knowledge management practitioner, I am a firm believer that good knowledge and insights can result in better policies and strategies. In this age where content is created by the masses, this ensures that materials presented in academic papers are well-justified with clear linkages to previously referenced knowledge. This due diligence ensures readers are not misled with ideas or concepts that lacked evidence.

2) THE BASICS OF ESSAY WRITING

‘An academic essay aims to persuade readers of an idea based on evidence’ (EUCLID 2021, 1).

This simple first statement struck me whilst reading the first chapter of the ACA-401 period one (1) course pack. It is a fundamental, often forgotten basic function of an academic essay.

As I read on through the chapter, I reflected on my past writings of non-academic essays, reports, and articles which I had written previously, including an article which I had contributed to a community journal. Some had been written based on personal instinct and past knowledge, whilst others had been substantiated with more rigorous research and insights. I realised that articles which had been supported with sufficient evidence had greater credibility, and received better responses from readers (EUCLID 2019, 2).

Another key takeaway from this chapter was the need to organise ideas prior to drafting and writing the essay. Whilst it would seem like common sense to organise (plan) before doing anything, I had a habit of writing on the fly. Hence this was a strange concept for me initially. Whilst I understood the value of it, it did not come naturally to me. Upon further study of the notes, I realised that this process of organising ideas would be more efficient, and the tips for effective writing (EUCLID 2019, 3) resonated well with me. These were useful reminders to not procrastinate, be comfortable working with paragraph segments, and revisions - whilst keeping the essay question in mind.

3) PLAGIARISM

Having worked in public and private corporations for the past 20 years, it is common and often encouraged to reuse templates and wordings from past project proposals and reports. This was seen as replicating the best practices at work and often, there is no compulsion to share whose templates and wordings have been reused. In academic writing, such practice would be seen as plagiarism and be considered unethical (EUCLID 2021, 5).

Beyond the ethical and fairness issues of plagiarism, I felt that giving credit to the original authors could in fact strengthen the position of the article. As mobile technology enables a culture of sharing videos, pictures and information found on the Internet, it has become increasingly difficult to discern the truths from falsehoods. Hence there is much value to have your essay be peer-reviewed or cite references to a peer reviewed essay. That said, I am still working on my application of appropriate formats for citing works and referencing.

4) WRITING STYLES

Whilst I am able to appreciate the differences between personal and academic writing styles, I find it would be most useful to provide a mix of both so as to engage the readers and provide good flow for readers (EUCLID 2021, 12). Amongst the listed rules of thumb for writing papers, I felt the need to write clearly (EUCLID 2021, 14-16) was most essential as it relates to a style of writing that is engaging, focused, aligned to the main thesis, and flows in support of assertions. Personally, I have read many papers which had been drowned by citations and quotations, such that the argument presented by the author gets lost.

5) STYLE GUIDE

Another concern I had, was the need to apply a specific style guide in writing my thesis. I was pleased to have read that the Turabian style was actually a simplified version of the Chicago Manual of Style (CMS) (EUCLID 2021, 44) and have found the crib sheet by Dr Abel Scribe in Chapter 8 of the course pack to be extremely useful in my understanding of how to apply CMS.

Whilst the similarities between Turabian and CMS are well depicted in the course pack, I decided to also explore the Oxford Style Guide to develop another perspective on how writing styles might differ. I felt that the Oxford Style was meant to establish consistency in internal presentations and written communications (Oxford 2016, 1) instead of proper academic writing. It was actually quite similar in style, as past writings at school or work. Hence, I think I will stick to the Turabian style for subsequent academic writings.

6) CONCLUSION

In a bid to conclude this response paper, I re-read the ACA-401 period one course pack and watched the 14-minute video for a third time. I have a newfound appreciation for academic rigour, and the value it brings to foster a common 'language' for communication. It will take much practice to be proficient in organising and structuring my ideas into a written document. It will take more time to ensure flow in the essay whilst providing substantiated evidence and citations. I look forward to honing my craft in the fundamentals of ACA-401, so as to support me for my study in EUCLID.

REFERENCES

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.